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● ***Gaurotina syamatarata* sp. nov., a new longicorn beetle inhabiting the dry hot valley of Sichuan, China (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: A new species of the genus *Gaurotina* Ganglbauer, 1889 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) is described and illustrated from Heishui County of Sichuan Province, China, viz. *Gaurotina syamatarata* sp. nov. Habitat photos and a distributional map are also provided.

Keywords: Lepturinae, longicorn beetles, morphology, Rhagiini, taxonomy

● **中国四川干热河谷一天牛新种——绿度母瘤花天牛（鞘翅目，天牛科）**

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摘要：本文描述了一个中国四川省黑水县的瘤花天牛属新种，即绿度母瘤花天牛。此外，文中还提供了新种的生境照及分布图。

关键词：花天牛亚科，天牛，形态学，皮花天牛族，分类学

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● Introduction

The endemic Chinese genus *Gaurotina* Ganglbauer, 1889 was established for *Gaurotina superba* Ganglbauer, 1889 from Gansu Province, China, hitherto containing seven recognized species. (Danilevsky & Rapuzzi 1996; Lin 2020; Tavakilian & Chevillotte 2025).

During a field survey in western Sichuan in early summer of 2025, a female rhagiine adult was collected by the author. After checking the morphological characteristics, the specimen was identified as a new *Gaurotina* species. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to describe the new species, *Gaurotina syamatara* **sp. nov.** Diagnosis, habitat and distribution of the new species are also provided.

● Material and methods

Specimen examined in this study was deposited in the Collection of Forest Entomology Laboratory, Beijing Forestry University, Beijing, China (CBFU). The labels of the specimen are cited verbatim. Detailed information of each label is listed in quotation marks (“”). Individual labels are separated by double slashes (/). Author’s notes are in brackets ([]). The habitus photographs were taken using a Nikon D7100 camera with LAOWA 60 mm F/2.8 2× Ultra Macro lens. For each final image, several photographs were taken at different focal planes and combined using Zerene Stacker to get one synthesized photograph. The distribution map was made with QGIS 3.28. All images were finally modified and arranged into plates by Adobe Photoshop CC 2019.

● Taxonomy

Tribe Rhagiini Kirby, 1837

Genus *Gaurotina* Ganglbauer, 1889

Ganglbauer, 1889: 49; **Type species:** *Gaurotina superba* Ganglbauer, 1889.

Gaurotina syamatara Chen, **sp. nov.** 绿度母瘤花天牛

<https://zoobank.org/B8975954-DAEE-40DD-AACF-073FA4658897>

Figs 1–3

Type material. Holotype: ♀ (CBFU), labeled “Sichuan, Aba pref., Heishui county, Se’ergu town, dry-hot valley, 31.9299 N, 103.4227E, 1770 m // Night on ground, 2025.V.31; Hongliang Shi, Tao Li, Jiaheng Chen, Zouyan Wu lgt.”.

Description. Female. Body length 16.3 mm, width (elytral width at humeri) 6.7 mm.

Color. Head brownish-yellow; terminal maxillary and labial palpomeres dark brown, the other palpomeres brownish-yellow; antennomeres 1–2 and proximal third of antennomere 3 brownish-yellow, the other antennomeres blackish-brown; pronotum brownish-yellow, with disc blurredly black; scutellum black; elytra with bluish green metallic luster (greener in life Fig. 2D); ventral surface brownish-yellow; tibiae and base of femora brownish-yellow, main part of femora and tarsi dark brown, ventral surface of tibiae blurredly black at proximal half.

Head. Mandibles dorsally glabrous, laterally pubescent and punctate (Fig. 1B); labrum and clypeus transverse and punctate, with fine recumbent grayish-yellow pubescence; frons densely punctate, with a deep and narrow median groove extending from anterior margin to vertex; vertex coarsely and densely punctate; tempora not swelling gradually constricted to neck; eyes large; antennae long, aligned backward reaching apical fourth of elytra, ratio of relative lengths of antennomeres 1–11 as follows: 48: 11: 39: 45: 79: 72 :74: 67: 62: 60: 62.

Pronotum (Fig. 2A). Length / basal width 0.83; anterior margin curved, posterior margin bisinuate; posterior angles obtuse; pronotum deeply constricted near apical fourth and basal third, both forming a transverse wide groove; one lateral tubercle and one dorsolateral tubercle present each side, width between tips of dorsolateral tubercles equal to basal width, the dorsolateral tubercle slightly larger than the lateral tubercle, the tip of lateral tubercle exposed in dorsal view; one pair of deep foveae present at dorsal base of dorsolateral tubercles; anterior margin,

discal area between two transverse grooves and posterior margin finely and sparsely punctate, punctures pubescent, smooth in transvers grooves.

FIGURE 1. Habitus of *G. syamatarata* **sp. nov.**, holotype, ♀: **A** dorsal view **B** left lateral view **C** ventral view. Scale bar = 5.0 mm.

Elytra. Length / humeral width 1.69; pronotal basal width / humeral width 0.53; humeri prominent; lateral margins straight; conjointly rounded at apices (Fig. 2C); dorsal surface shiny and punctate dense, punctures pubescent, dense but evenly distributed, proximally coarsest, gradually finer to distal apices.

Ventral side. Intercoxal process of metasternum distinctly wider than that of mesosternum, both apically truncated.

Legs. Legs slender; metatarsomere 1 slightly longer than following two tarsomeres combined.

Female genitalia. Coxite lobe and stylus as in Fig. 2B.

Male. Unknown.

Diagnosis. Among all congeneric species, *G. syamatarata* **sp. n.** can be easily reminiscent of *G. nitida* Gressitt, 1951 for their shiny bodies and similar color assortments, but distinguished from the latter by the combination of following characters: (1) larger size, body length 16.3 mm (versus 12.5 mm in *G. nitida*); (2) only antennomeres 1–2 and proximal third of antennomere 3 brownish-yellow (versus antennomeres 1–4 and proximal half of antennomere 5 brownish yellow in *G. nitida*); (3) antennae aligned backward reaching apical fourth of elytra (versus that of *G. nitida* attaining elytral apices); (4) head with vertex coarsely and densely punctate at least (versus almost smooth, impunctate in *G. nitida*); (5) pronotal disc black blurredly (versus yellowish brown in *G. nitida*); (6) main part of femora (except for the femoro-tibial joint namely) and tarsi dark brown (versus entirely yellow in *G. nitida*).

FIGURE 2. Characters of *G. syamatarā* sp. nov.: **A** pronotum **B** coxite lobe and stylus **C** elytral apex **D** elytral color in life. Scale bar = 1.0 mm for A, C; = 0.2 mm for B.

Etymology. The specific epithet is from “Śyāmatārā”, the Sanskrit name of Green Tara, a bodhisattva embodying compassionate action in Tibetan Buddhism. It references the bluish-green elytra of the species, reminiscent of the bodhisattva’s traditional depictions, and the type locality where Tibetan Buddhist culture prevails. The name is treated as a noun in apposition.

Distribution (Fig. 3). CHINA: Sichuan, Heishui.

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FIGURE 3. Habitat and distribution of *G. syamatarata* sp. nov.: **A** distribution, concentric circle: type locality **B** fresh specimen **C** microenvironment of the type locality (Photograph taken by Ze-Xun Yang) **D** general environment of Se'ergu Town (Photograph taken by Tian-Xuan Gu).

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● Additional information

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